

New records of *Platyceps najadum* (Eichwald, 1831) (Reptilia: Colubridae) in Bulgaria

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Information concerning the distribution of *Platyceps najadum* (Eichwald, 1831) in Bulgaria was summarized by NAUMOV & STANCHEV (2004. Amphibians and reptiles in Bulgaria and the Balkan Peninsula. Accessible online at: www.herpetology.hit.bg). In this short note we announce seventeen new localities recorded in the period 1993-2006 (Fig. 1): Churilovo, Ograzhden Mts. (UTM: FL69; 800 m a.s.l.) – 1 ad., 26.04.2004 (N. Tz. observed); Yakovo, Ograzhden Mts. (FL79; 850 m) – 1 juv., 28.04.2004 (N. Tz. obs.); Lebnitsa River valley below Sestrino, Ograzhden Mts. (FL89; 250 m) – 1 ad., 29.04.2004 (N. Tz. obs.); Kozhuha Hill, Struma River Valley (FL89; 150-200 m) – 3 ad. and 1 juv., 04.1993 (B. N. obs.); Moravska, Maleshevska Mts. (FM71; 700 m) – 1 subad., 17.06.1994 (N. Tz. obs.); between villages of Goreme and Vrakupovitsa, Maleshevska Mts. (FM71; 800 m) – 1 ad., 18.06.1994 (N. Tz. obs.); 2.5 km southwest of Stara Kresna, Kresna Gorge (FM82; 420 m) – 1 ad. (found dead on the road), 03.06.2003 (M. Langourov obs.); 300 m west of the mouth of Rachkin dol River, Kresna Gorge (FM73; 350 m) – 2 ad., 11.05.2001 (B. N. and M. Naumova obs.); 1.5 km southwest of Lilyanovo, Pirin Mts. (FM90; 450 m) – 1 ad., 12.05.2001 (B. N. and M. Stanchev obs.); Predela Place, Pirin Mts. (FM94, 900 m) – 1 ad. (found dead on the road), 06.2005 (A. S. obs.); a gully east of Vukovo, Boboshevo Gorge (FM67; 700 m) – 2 ad., 06.06.2004 (N. Tz. obs.); 1 km northwest of Byaga, Besaparski Heights (KG86; 350 m) – 1 ad., 17.05.2002 (M. Naumova and B. N. obs.); Byalgradets, Eastern Rhodopes Mts. (MF08, 225 m) – 1 ad., 04.09.2005 (N. Tz. obs.); Belopolyane, Eastern Rhodopes Mts. (MF29, 200 m) – 1 ad., 08.09.2005 (N. Tz. obs.); the fortress south of Mezek, Eastern Rhodopes

Fig 1. Distribution of *P. najadum* in Bulgaria by UTM grid 10X10 km.

Mts. (MG22, 237 m) – 5 ad., 08.05.2005 (N. Tz. and B. Petrov obs.); 3 km southeast from Lesovo, Dervent Heights (MG64; 300 m) – 1 ad., 09.08.2005 (N. Tz. obs.); the slope of Bakadzhit site Hills east of Pobeda (MG79; 350 m) – 1 subad., 18.05.2003 (N. Tz. obs.).

The new localities widen the knowledge on the distribution of *P. najadum* in Bulgaria and some of them are of importance for tracing the northern border of the species range. The locality Predela is the highest one in the country and the locality Pobeda is the northeasternmost* in the species range in the Balkan Peninsula.

* The locality Sozopol (UTM: NG59), mentioned by SCHLÜTER (2006. Die Herpetofauna der bulgarischen Schwarzmeerküste - Teil 3: Schlangen. – *Elaphe*, 14 (2): 59-66.) remains to be confirmed.